

Frustration and Aggression as Contributors to Examination Malpractice Among Secondary School Students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State

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Abstract

This study investigated frustration and aggression as contributors to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. A sample of 322 respondents from a total population of 3,218 students was selected for the study using Nworgu (1991) 16% representative sample size formula. A self-designed 10-items four point modified rating type scale questionnaire titled "Frustration and Aggression as Contributors to Examination Malpractice among Students Questionnaire" (FACESQ) was used for data collection. Data obtained for the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while chi-square (χ^2) goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that frustration and aggression contribute significantly to examination malpractice among secondary school students. Based on the findings, recommendations were made such as counsellors should assist students to make profitable use of time, work harder and pass examinations without cheating and violent acts.

Keywords: Aggression, Examination Malpractice, Frustration, Secondary School Students

Introduction

One canker worm that has deeply eaten the Nigerian educational system is examination malpractice. Examination malpractice has been a social problem for decades. The rate and manner it is perpetrated nowadays calls for serious concern. Examination malpractice is common everywhere and every examination season witnesses the emergence of new ways of cheating (Nnam & Inah, 2015). The recurring cases of examination malpractice in recent times has become

a thing of concern to stakeholders such as parents, teachers, school administrators and others as the credibility and quality of Nigerian certificates are threatened. According to Gbenda (2008:28), an examination malpractice occurs “when an individual abandons the rigours of study and depends instead on fraudulent means to pass examinations”. This means that examination malpractice is the process of using shortcut and dubious ways to achieve success in examination. Examination malpractice can be defined as using illegal means to secure undue advantage at an examination in order to be successful (Yakubu & Idoko 2014). Ifijeh, Michael-Onuoha, Ilogho and Osinuu (2015) defined examination malpractice as dishonest practice that encompasses any action by an individual or group of students to gain an undue advantage in any form of assessment, be it course work tests or examinations. Examination malpractice therefore, refers to any unauthorized and dishonoured act engaged by learners to make unjustified progress in test or examination.

Globally, evidence abounds of increasing incidents of examination malpractice by learners in primary, secondary schools as well as tertiary institutions of learning. According to Malunga (2000) every year, the Malawi National Examination Board (MANEB) deals with cases of unscrupulous school administrators, teachers, parents and students involved in examination malpractice. Similarly, the trend of examination malpractice was reported to be on the increase in Pakistan (Munachaonga, 2014).

However, in Nigeria, the first case of examination malpractice was recorded in 1914 when Cambridge School Certificate Examination was leaked to candidates. In 1948, a Nigerian candidate’s result was cancelled because of his possession of notes already prepared and taken to the examination hall of the Cambridge examination. Expo, 1977 was so popular in Nigeria. It was as a result of the unprecedented leakages of the West African Examination Council’s May/June examination question papers that year. Similarly, in 2004 examination malpractice index was high (58.3%) in 13 states of the federation. The states include Abia, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Ebony, Enugu, Imo, Kaduna, Kogi, Kwara, Rivers, Zamfara. The federal capital territory Abuja came least with 0.9% (Vanguard Newspaper 2004).

In Kogi State, WAEC has derecognized thirteen secondary schools and warned fifty six others for their involvement in examination malpractice such as the use of mobile phones and copying each other’s work during the 2018 West Africa senior school certificate examinations (WASSCE). Some students in Olamaboro Local Government Area run from their original schools in towns to miracle centres to register for their Senior School Certificates Examination. In order to meet the demand of the dubious centres, some of the students may engage in stealing or even lie to their parents/guardians, some of the students may due to annoyance, insult, bully and threaten any invigilator, students, staff who stand in their ways with dangerous weapons such as knives, bottles of acid and cutlasses. This may be as a result of lack confidence to write examination and make beautiful grades through their own efforts.

According to Anderson and Bushman (2002), frustration occurs when an individual continues an action in the expectation of gratification or desired goal but does not actually attain it. Denga (1998) asserted that frustrated students act as if they have schizophrenia, an extreme mental ill health that threatens the existence of self and others. They lack self confidence in their

own efforts and have to beef up their confidence by obtaining extra help from another student to add to what they know. They can thus take arms against whatever appears to be threatening their well-being. This is to say that, students who obtained results through short cut are being punished psychologically as they have beautiful results that might not be used to secure jobs. Similarly, Denga (2001) stated that frustration has been shown to be an important psychological source of aggressive behaviour. According to the author, when individuals are frustrated in their attempt to attain their objectives, they certainly revolt against the source they feel blocks their chances of getting what they desire. It must therefore be reiterated that students who have suffered any form of frustration towards achieving academic objectives, job opportunities and the like look for opportunities to revenge or vent it out on what they suspect or know is the cause of their frustration. Students who are frustrated often manifest the following behaviours, passive aggressive behaviours, inability to control one's actions, headache and so on. Frustration therefore refers to manifestation of defeats arising from hindrance of needs.

According to Reel in Aderounmu (2004), frustration can arise from an environmental thwarting of one's desires or it may result from an internal motivational conflict. Students' awareness of the high rate of failure recorded from Senior Secondary School Examinations and the problems created for candidates such as unemployment, inability to go for further studies and undue castigation from parents and relatives may lead to frustration on their parts. Frustration can be disruptive, displaying inappropriate behaviour which are expressed through some forms of examination malpractice. These students indulge in examination misconduct to get suitable jobs, further their education and probably please their parents and friends.

A Frustrated student faces serious challenges during examinations. When students lack confidence in themselves, they may resort to cheating during examination. Some of the students may totally give up the hope of passing examination through their own efforts. Frustration is a behaviour associated with not achieving a particular goal. It is manifested in oppressive fear, worry, despair, anger and the likes. It could push some students to all kinds of antisocial acts such examination malpractice (Ramalingam, 2006).

Aggression has been defined as a "hostile behaviour which may be physical or verbal directed either at others or self" (Ramalingam, 2006). It is further characterized by strong-self-assertion with hostile or harmful tones. Under some circumstances, aggression may be normal reaction to a threat, anger, confusion, discomfort, fear, over stimulation and tiredness can lead to aggressive reactions. According to Bandura, (1973), aggression is a behavior that results in personal injury and in destruction of property. The injury may be psychological (in the form of devaluation or degradation) as well as physical. This is why hostile behaviours by examination cheats posed a lot of threat to their mates, thereby creating fear and making them to dislike the school premises and virtually everything in school. This state of affairs hampers smooth teaching and learning in schools. Aggression therefore means destructive action exhibited towards self and others.

According to Omoregie (2005) aggressive students like destroying school property at the slightest provocation, intimidate and threaten other students, break into principal's office to forge school leaving testimonials, and break into "bursars" offices to steal money to pay for the

exorbitant examinations. Examination malpractice leads to uncertainty, insecurity, fear, panic, anxiety and anarchy at examination centres, thereby making such examination centres uncondusive for innocent candidates due to the activities of examination cheats, who try as much as possible to create pandemonium so as to achieve their illicit plans. This was supported by Aigbekaen (2007) who indicated that candidates come into examination halls with dangerous weapons like knives, bottles of acid, guns and others which they secretly show supervisors and invigilators as a way of getting them intimidated. This is to say that examination cheats exhibit these hostile behaviours to scare and intimidate class mates, friends and others so that even when they are seen indulging in the act of copying or cheating no one has the courage to report or raise alarm. From the above findings, it can be said that examination cheats may be pre-disposed to violent act as a result of not being able to achieve their goals (defending their certificates).

Statement of the Problem

Examination malpractice is becoming a serious social problem and a source of concern to stakeholders in education. The researchers observed that a lot of students who have made fantastic results through examination malpractice have become disappointments to themselves, parents and the society in general. They may become frustrated completely due to inability to graduate from tertiary institutions. Others who managed to graduate may lack the ability to defend certificates obtained. They might not be able to meet challenges of work interview as they lack proper self-expression and construction. All of this may eventually lead to aggressive tendencies to fellow students, school authorities and the society at large.

Although, several studies have been carried out on examination malpractice and its attendant negative impacts on the educational system globally including Nigeria and the study area in particular, little attention has been made by researchers on the contributions of frustration and aggression to examination malpractice among secondary school students in study area. This is the gap the researchers intend to fill.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the contributions of frustration and aggression to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State. To achieve this purpose, the following specific objectives were raised:

1. Determine the contribution of frustration to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi state.
2. Investigate the contribution of aggression to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised;

1. What is the contribution of frustration to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro local government area of Kogi State?
2. What is the contribution of aggression tendencies to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro local government area of Kogi State?

Research Hypotheses

For the purpose of this study, the following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Frustration has no significant contribution to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. Aggression has no significant contribution to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Methodology

The design that used in carrying out this study was the descriptive survey. Descriptive survey design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be a representative of the entire group (Emaikwu,2015). This design was therefore relevant to this study since the representative of students were sampled from larger population to answer questions relating to impacts of frustration and aggression tendencies on examination malpractice among secondary school students of Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State. The total population of this study was 3,218 senior secondary school students from Olamaboro Local Government area of Kogi State. The sample for the study comprised 322 senior secondary school students from the study area which is 10% of the study population. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select the senior secondary school students for this study.

A structured questionnaire titled "Frustration and Aggression as Contributors to Examination Malpractice among Students Questionnaire" (FACSQ) was used to for data collection. A total number of 10 items were presented as statements to which respondents were required to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on a four point modified Likert type scale as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) - 4, Agree (A) -3, Disagree (D) -2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1. Face and content validation of the instrument was done by three experts in guidance and counselling, in the Department of Educational Foundations, Benue State University, Makurdi. The Reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach-Alpha Coefficient and the test yielded a reliability coefficient of .77.The instrument was therefore adjudged to have a high level of reliability and can be used for the study. The researchers personally administered and collected data with the assistance of three research assistants. The retrieval was done through the research assistants the following day. A total number of 322 questionnaires were administered and retrieved. The data collected were analyzed using frequency count, percentages and mean for the research questions. The mean of 2.50 was taken as criterion for determination of impact while a

cutoff point of 2.50 and above represent positive responses while anything less than 2.50 was regarded as negative responses. The inferential statistics of chi-square (χ^2) goodness of fit test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Results

Results of the study were obtained from the research questions answered through data collected.

Research Question One: What is the contribution of frustration to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro local government area of Kogi State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Responses of Students on the Contributions of Frustration to Examination Malpractice among Secondary School Students

S/N	Questionnaire items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean (\bar{X})	ST.D	Decision
1	Frustration makes students not to have confidence in themselves.	91	193	28	10	3.13	.69	Agreed
2	Students who indulge in Examination malpractice are never happy.	143	163	10	6	3.38	.64	Agreed
3	Students who cheat in examination always exhibit self-defeat.	181	101	32	8	3.41	.77	Agreed
4	Frustration makes students to blame teachers/examiners for poor performance.	98	188	22	14	3.15	.72	Agreed
5	Students who are involved in examination malpractice always complain of everything during examinations.	187	100	23	12	3.43	.78	Agreed
Cluster mean standard Deviation						3.30	0.72	Agreed

Table 2 indicated that, frustration has negative contribution to examination malpractice among secondary school students in the study areas. This was shown by the cluster mean 3.30 and standard deviation 0.72 which was higher than the cutoff point of 2.50.

Research Question Two: What is the contribution of aggression to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro local government area of Kogi State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Responses of Students on Contribution of Aggression to Examination Malpractice among Secondary School Students

S/N	Questionnaire items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean (X)	St.d	Decision
6	Examination cheats exhibit violent behaviours during examination.	173	101	20	28	3.30	.93	Agreed
7	Examination cheats are never friendly and so, bully others.	158	120	24	20	3.29	.85	Agreed
8	Students who indulge in examination malpractice like rowdy environment, so that they can perpetrate their evil acts.	180	95	29	18	3.36	.86	Agreed
9	Examination cheats derive pleasure from frightening others, so as to secure recognition from others.	153	128	31	10	3.32	.77	Agreed
10	Examination cheats show hostility towards authority and so break school rules and regulations.	181	110	18	13	3.43	.77	Agreed
Cluster mean and standard deviation						3.34	0.84	Agreed

Table 3 showed that, aggression contributes negatively to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Areas of Kogi State. The cluster mean of 3.34 and standard deviation of 0.84 also showed that all the items were rated above 2.50 cut off point. This implied that secondary school students perceived the negative contribution of aggression to examination malpractice in the study areas.

Hypothesis 1: Frustration has no significant contribution to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Table 3: Chi-square of the Contributions of Frustration to Examination Malpractice among Secondary School Students

Responses	Observed freq	Expected freq	Df	Level of sig.	Cal. X ²	Crit. X ²	Decision
Strongly Disagree	12	80.5	3	0.05	244.98	7.82	Rejected
Disagree	23	80.5					
Agree	100	80.5					
Strongly Agree	187	80.5					

Value in parentheses are percentages ($X^2 = 244.98$, $df = 3$, $p = .000 < .05$)

Table 3, indicated the chi-square value of 244.98 at df of 3 and $P = .000 < .05$ to be statistically significant. The null hypothesis which stated that frustration was not significantly perceived as a contributor to examination malpractice among secondary school students was therefore rejected. This implied that frustration has negative contributions to examination malpractice among secondary school students in the study areas.

Hypothesis 2: Aggression has no significant contribution to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Table 4: Chi-square test of the Contributions of Aggression to Examination Malpractice among Secondary School Students.

Responses	Observed freq	Expected freq	Df	Level of sig.	Cal. X ²	Crit. X ²	Decision
Strongly Disagree	13	80.5	3	0.05	241.40	7.82	Rejected
Disagree	18	80.5					
Agree	110	80.5					
Strongly Agree	181	80.5					

Value in parentheses are percentages ($X^2 = 241.40$, $df = 3$, $p = .000 < .05$)

Table 4, showed the chi-square value of 241.40 at df of 3 and $P = .000 < .05$ to be statistically significant. The null hypothesis which stated that aggression was not significantly perceived as a contributor to examination malpractice of among secondary school students was therefore rejected. This implied that secondary school students significantly perceived the negative contribution of aggression to examination malpractice.

Major Findings of the Study

1. Frustration contributes significantly to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. Aggression significantly contributes to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the contributions of frustration and aggression to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local government Area of Kogi state. As a result of the analysis of the two research questions and two hypotheses of the investigation, the discussion of findings is as beneath.

Hypothesis one indicated that, frustration has significant contributions to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State. This finding is consistent with Denga, (1998) who asserted that frustrated student act as if they have schizophrenia, an extreme mental ill health that threatens the existence of self and others. They lack self confidence in their own efforts and have to beef up their confidence by obtaining extra help from another student to add to what they know. They can thus take arms against whatever appears to be threatening their well-being. The finding is in agreement with Abdulwahab, (2005) who posited that frustration often leads students to all kinds of anti-social vices such as examination malpractice. The findings aligned with Reel in Aderounmu, (2004) who stated that frustration can arise from an environmental thwarting of one's desires or it may result from an internal motivational conflict.

Hypothesis two indicated that aggression contributes significantly to examination malpractice among secondary school students in Olamaboro Local Government Area of Kogi State. This finding is in line with Omoregie (2005) who revealed that students who engage in examination malpractice destroy school properties at the slightest provocation, intimidate and threaten other students who did not join them in cheating, break into principal's office to forge school leaving testimonials, and break into "bursars" offices to steal money to pay for the exorbitant examinations. Examination malpractice leads to uncertainty, insecurity, fear, panic, anxiety and anarchy at examination centers, thereby making such centers inconclusive for innocent candidates due to the activities of examination cheats, who try as much as possible to create pandemonium so as to achieve their illicit plans. The result is in consonance with Aigbekaen, (2007) who indicated that candidates come into examination halls with dangerous weapons like knives, bottles of acid, guns and others which they secretly show supervisors and invigilators as a way of getting them intimidated to carry out their illicit act.

Conclusion

Frustration and aggression have been identified as contributors to examination malpractice among secondary school students in the study area. Since counseling is identified as a viable tool in assisting individuals to become better and useful, the counsellor can be of help to students in this regard.

1. The counsellor can assist students to overcome frustration by helping them to develop positive self-concept, self-confidence to work hard and write examinations without cheating.
2. Students could be assisted through counselling to develop sound moral values that might repel aggression from their lives. This may go a long way in curbing examination malpractice among students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Counsellors should assist students to make profitable use of time, work harder and pass examinations without cheating.
2. Students should be counselled to desist from bullying, fighting, and threatening school mates, teachers and invigilators as a means of intimidating them to perpetrate the selfish act of cheating in examinations.

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